

International Journal of Emerging Trends in Education

www.ijete.org.pk

Research Article

Role of Self-Studies in Promoting Learning among Students at University Level

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Article Info.	Abstract
Received: 17-Apr-23 Revised: 16-Jun-23 Accepted: 2-Jul-23 Published: 9-Jul-23	The purpose of this study was to investigate the role and impact of self-studies on learning among students at the Mansoura University, Egypt. The study utilized a survey method and was descriptive in nature. The population of the study comprised all 836 students in the University Development Center, with a sample size of 220 students selected using simple random sampling technique. A five-point Likert Scale questionnaire was used to collect data on the role and impact of self-studies on learning. The collected data was analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS), with simple mean, frequency, and percentage used for the analysis. The findings suggest that incorporating critical thinking into daily lessons and encouraging students to take responsibility for their own learning can enhance self-studies. It is recommended that further research should be conducted to better understand how students perceive responsibility for their own learning to create a conducive learning environment in the classroom.
Keywords:	Self-studies, Retrieval Practice, Elaborative Self-explanation, Interleaved Practice, University Level
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How to Cite:	Mitwally. M. A. A. (2023). Role of Self-Studies in Promoting Learning among Students at University Level. <i>International Journal of Emerging Trends in Education</i> , 1(1), 38-47.

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INTRODUCTION

Learning is a natural process that occurs in all living organisms, including humans and animals. It plays a crucial role in the growth and development of children, who acquire new habits through learning and imitation of traditions and customs. Intellectual abilities, moral judgement, conceptions of justice, and artistic sensibility are all fostered by learning. Lifelong learning is a continuous process that impacts our personalities, ambitions, attitudes, beliefs, language, and traditions, among other things. Psychology is centered around the concept of learning, and human development is heavily influenced by it. Many psychologists have put forth various theories on how learning occurs. At its core, learning is a change in behavior that results from experience. As children are exposed to their environment, they modify their behavior accordingly. Learning is responsible for every thought and action a learner has, and it is a long-lasting change that can even affect the learner's personality traits (Lewin, 2014).

Learning is the modification of behavior because of experience. The child modifies his behavior as a result of his exposure to the environment. Every action or thought a learner has been because of learning. Learning is a somewhat long-lasting change in the learner's behavior. Even the learner's personality qualities change as a result of it. Education is a difficult process. This might be characterized as a statement shift. Over time, behavior changes somewhat permanently, and knowledge plays a role in some of these changes. It may lead to the acquisition of fresh knowledge, principles, impressions, skills for learning, and facts. The numerous teaching-learning resources reinforce learning by stimulating, motivating, and temporarily focusing the learner's attention during the teaching process (Chorley, 2005). Successful independent study requires students to possess a range of skills and attitudes towards learning. To this end, students must reflect on their past experiences with autonomous learning, as well as consider their current situation, study habits, family circumstances, and support systems at both home and school. In contrast to being confined to the material presented by their teachers and textbooks, students are encouraged to explore subjects of personal interest through self-study. This practice helps them develop stronger study skills and gain a deeper understanding of the subject matter (Bangert, 2011).

Self-studying learning is a learning strategy in which students manage their own learning outside of the classroom and without oversight. Self-study can be a very beneficial technique for many students to learn because they can control what they are studying. To make the most of your child's learning experience, combine self-study and conventional classroom instruction. Collectively, these strategies aid pupils in learning and memory retention, which improves comprehension, academic performance, and motivation (Roediger, 2007). Self-study is the capacity to support oneself on one's own. It also establishes what a particular student needs to study and how that student wishes to clearly complete their learning. It also demonstrates how a student use various learning strategies to evaluate his own studies. Self-study is gaining popularity as a method for keeping students interested in what they are learning in class. Now that students have so many resources at their disposal, learning can take place outside of the classroom at any time (Coburn, 2009).

Effective learning involves a lot of self-studies. Even when using traditional teaching methods, it is crucial for students to have a thorough comprehension of each concept. The current study has a university-level concentration. The study is important because it sheds light on the phenomena of self-directed learning among college students. It is intended to outline the typical behavior of university students in terms of how they manage their daily lives to get a better education

(Willingham, 2013). The study of self-study learning is becoming increasingly important in the disciplines of psychology and education. Because of its crucial significance in the learning process, this topic has attracted the attention of numerous academics worldwide. In the discussion of the teaching-learning process, curriculum planners are assuming a significant role as the phenomenon of self-studies learning. Self-study is an individual effort to learn by references/experimentation or a required course. It can involve studying through books, some online journals, or using tutorials to understand a specific topic. In general, self-learning is more efficient than traditional classroom instruction since it is not simply more convenient for learners (Johnson, 2009).

Self-learning enables students to achieve greater marks on their assignments and tests, improving their cumulative grades. When deciding if a student is a good fit for the incoming freshman class, universities take their high school grades into account. In reality, universities consider a student's performance from their freshman year, emphasizing the value of independent study throughout high school (Maudsley, 2010). The only way to truly reform and enhance the university education system is to modify and improve the whole education system. It is critical for a student to have a clear idea and vision of self-study. Everything in the classroom is learned and understood by the students. Students need to review the topic after the lecture to ensure that they have a thorough comprehension of the material. At the university level, the concept of self-study is a critical component in increasing student confidence and strengthening teacher-student relationships. The objective of improving educational quality cannot be realized without self-study.

Research objectives

1. To find out the practices of self-studies learning among students at Mansoura University.
2. To examine the role of self-studies in promoting learning among students at University level.

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

Learning

Learning is the process of changing behavior as a result of experience. The child modifies his behavior as a result of his exposure to the environment. Over time, behavior changes somewhat permanently, and knowledge plays a role in some of these changes. It may lead to the acquisition of fresh knowledge, principles, impressions, skills for learning, and facts. The numerous teaching-learning resources reinforce learning by stimulating, motivating, and temporarily focusing the learner's attention during the teaching process (Chorley, 2005). Learning can be reinforced with different learning assets as they strategize, as they focus on the teaching method for a while. Visual aids stimulate student enthusiasm and help instructors articulate ideas effectively. Development ought to help the teacher in making a local area situated learning condition.

Learning peculiarity is vital for the improvement of people (McMillan, 2017). The combination of innovation in educational modules, means using it as a tool to showcase academic subjects and to advance high application thinking abilities about undergraduates. Modern developments in Pakistan have positively affected the state of undergraduate education. Changes in guidelines for improving skills initiatives initiated by the Ministry of Higher Education have enhanced the study hall learning situation in Pakistan. World-class state-of-the-art training aids were provided to the college study halls to make the home storage learning process interesting and exciting. In any case, the use of prospectus-based, indivisible assets is recommended (Ericsson, 2005).

Self-Study

Self-study is one of the main things not exclusively to meet all requirements for an assessment, however procuring viable methodology of hypothetical information is generally significant. One can figure out the idea according to his perspective, with his own models as opposed to any complicated model showed by the speaker. As indicated by analysts no two people are similar. There are individual contrasts. The people contrast in their propensities, interest's, thoughts, considerations, activities, mentalities, aptitudes, sentiments and so forth. In a class, understudies likewise vary in their propensities, perspectives, past information, knowledge (Rau, 2013). Self-study materials foster character attributes self-dependence, self-reliance, self-certainty among the students. It creates inventiveness among the students and makes them research arranged. It widens the psychological skyline of the students. By the assistance of self-study materials, the mental ability of the student creates and could be utilized for getting information and data. The self-study technique makes the students to use the relaxation time appropriately to improve and expand their asset of information and data as well as improve the learning among students (Butler, 2011).

Role of Teachers to Enhance Self-Study

Particularly for students in higher professional universities, teachers ought to reinforce the development of students' ability to learn, and assist them with developing trust in learning. Thus, teachers take on various strategies for training for various students, and show students as per their inclination. Teachers' ought to urge each understudy to study as indicated by their major interest, and to track down significant ways and objectives to advance the development of students (Rostan, 2010). To prepare the excitement of students, teacher ought to enhance different showing techniques in the class, for example, the utilization of flipped homeroom strategy, leave the assignment for the students, let them see before class, find the data, let the students talk each other in class, the teacher tuning in, students can utilize study hall content (Eyyam, 2014).

Students can make ideas, examine with each other, and gain from one another, eventually, teachers can give remarks or accomplishments in light of the exhibition of students, which can be utilized as the assessment reason for the graduation of the last of students. Moreover, teachers will further develop their showing level through the interest of Miniature Course Online Video and MOOC (Florez, 2011). College ought to effectively make conditions for teachers to regularly learn and trade encounters. College ought to likewise give more open doors to teachers to learn and dominate different speculations, let them comprehend and dominate the hypotheses, information and abilities expected to do independent mastering exercises (Kallweit, 2009). The chief occupation of educators is to propel care in understudies about self-studies. To associate with understudies in self-focuses on practices like point discussion is one of the huge parts while learning through self-studies. Further, per clients who make requests from discussions make careful different per clients to end up being incredible per clients. It is in like manner an educator's responsibility to attract understudies in pack discussions through self-focuses on strategies (Layman, 2015).

Role of Self Study at Higher Level

Self-studying is an unimaginable technique in which understudy can involve to redesign their chance for development, whether they are studying for a course or looking into a point for not a great explanation. Self-review allows students to expand their knowledge beyond what is presented in their class textbooks and by their teachers. Through the practice of self-study, students are encouraged to delve deeper into topics that they find interesting, which can strengthen their study skills. One of the significant benefits of self-study is that it empowers students to take ownership

of their own learning. When students have control over their learning, they become more enthusiastic about it (Eslaminejad, 2016). Self-study involves seeking out new information on a topic that a student is interested in, which allows them to learn beyond what is taught in the classroom. Through self-study, students can become more independent learners, as they take the initiative to seek out information on their own. As students engage in self-study and develop their independence, they begin to see themselves as capable of learning new things without the assistance of others. This newfound sense of autonomy can be a significant source of motivation for students (Vohs, 2010). Self-study allows students to learn at their own pace, focusing on the areas that interest them the most or require further understanding. This can help reduce feelings of frustration, anxiety, or boredom that students may experience in a traditional classroom setting. Interest is a crucial factor in motivating students to learn. When students are not engaged with what they are studying, they are less likely to retain the information. They learn to memorize rather than truly understand. Self-study, on the other hand, allows students to select topics they are enthusiastic about and eager to learn, resulting in a more productive and fulfilling learning experience (Tuckman, 2008).

Self-study is a significant part of successful learning. In any event, studying with traditional showing techniques, a student should have an unmistakable vision and comprehension of each. You can't learn and comprehend everything in that frame of mind, after your talk you should update point for the unmistakable comprehension of the subjects. It is vital for students showing up in serious tests to self-study and be careful with the points to show up in the thorough addressing of rivalry and to proceed decisively (Pintrich, 2013).

Strategies to Enhance Self-Study

Retrieval Practice

Tests are frequently solely used to evaluate what a student has realized or potentially to dole out a grade. A natural, however erroneous, supposition that will be that learning just happens during study meetings while tests are basically estimations which don't straightforwardly influence learning. To works on long haul learning and outflanks well known study strategies, for example, note-taking and restudying. With regards to the sort of tests, useful tests, for example, genuine inquiries and short-answer structures are liked over numerous decision tests. The explanation is that different decision tests just require the student to inactively perceive the right response, while creation tests require dynamic remaking of information from memory. Thusly, creation tests for the most part outflank acknowledgment tests and ought to be the favored arrangement if long haul learning is the primary objective. Despite the fact that tests are normally utilized by teachers, students can utilize self-testing or test one another. In opposition to prevalent thinking, recovery practice isn't just appropriate for learning disconnected realities, yet in addition animates profound learning and the exchange or information to different sorts of issues (Stokes, 2014).

Elaborative Self-explanation

Elaborative self-clarification is a study system which expects students to pose inquiries to themselves about the substance and their insight thereof. It is valuable for learning overall as well as move (i.e., the utilization of information to new issues). A direct technique for utilizing this study procedure is to give students a brief to concoct 'why' inquiries concerning the substance, which is useful for learning (Bullough, 2019). Utilizing inquiries to direct elaborative self-clarification and animating review from memory additionally sets off recovery practice, further

improving the advantages of this study system. While doing this, it is essential to zero in on inquiries concerning realities, however to particularly zero in on decisive reasoning inquiries pointed toward getting a profound comprehension of the material (Pinnegar, 2011).

Interleaved Practice

The concept of interleaved practice pertains to the organization of different sets of learning materials, in contrast to distributed practice which focuses on the timing and method of learning the same materials. Rather than grouping similar study problems together, interleaving them can lead to improved long-term retention of information. (e.g., ACBCAB) (Finley, 2005). In courses that focus on case studies or problem-solving, interleaved practice is particularly useful when multiple examples need to be analyzed, such as various mathematical equations or clinical scenarios. This learning strategy can be utilized by both students and instructors to improve the sequencing of problem types for better retention of information. It's important to remember that interleaving different types of tasks is more effective than interleaving different versions of the same task (Ruane, 2014).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study conducted was descriptive in nature and utilized a survey method to investigate the influence of self-study on learning at the university level. The population of the study was comprised of all 836 students in the University Development Center at the Mansoura University. A sample of 220 students was selected from various departments of the University Development Center using a simple random sampling technique. A five-point Likert Scale questionnaire was utilized as a research instrument to gather data on the role and impact of self-study on student learning. The questionnaire was validated by two experts from the University Development Center, Mansoura University and the reliability of the instrument was assessed using Cronbach's alpha statistical technique. The data were personally collected by the researcher from the students and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Frequency, percentage, and mean statistical techniques were employed to analyze the collected data.

RESULTS

Table 1: Mean analysis of Role of self-studies learning at university level

Statements	N	Mean
Self-studies helps the students to broaden their thinking level	220	4.45
Self-studies provide freedom to students to learn freely	220	4.77
Self-studies limit the interest of students	220	4.57
Self-studies is more fun than regular teaching	220	4.49
Self-studies build a sense of responsibility in the students	220	4.88
Self-studies boost the students' self-esteem	220	4.28
Self-studies students make their own study material	220	4.35
Self-studies helps the students in completing assignment	220	4.85
Self-studies helps the students to learn at their desired time	220	4.31
Self-studies students tend to retain more naturally in work	220	4.44
Self-studies gives opportunity to interact with the subject matter	220	4.30
Self-studies provides opportunity to develop good work ethic	220	4.88
Self-studies enhance self-confidence of students	220	4.21
Self-studies helps the student to perform well in tests	220	4.05

Self-studies encourages the curiosity in students	220	4.41
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Table 1 shows the mean score of Role of self-studies learning at university level. The table further represented that the mean score of Self-studies helps the students to broaden their thinking level; N=220, M=4.45, Self-studies provide freedom to students to learn freely; N=220, M= 4.77; Self-studies limit the interest of students; N=220, M= 4.57; Self-studies is more fun than regular teaching; N=220, M=4.49; Self-studies build a sense of responsibility in the students; N=220, M= 4.88; Self-studies boost the students’ self-esteem; N=220, M=4.28; Self-studies students make their own study material; N=220, M=4.35; Self-studies helps the students in completing assignment; N=220, M=4.85; Self-studies helps the students to learn at their desired time; N=220, M=4.31; Self-studies students tend to retain more naturally in work; N=220, M=4.44; Self-studies gives opportunity to interact with the subject matter; N=220, M=4.30, Self-studies provides opportunity to develop good work ethic; N=220, M=4.88; Self-studies enhance self-confidence of students; N=220, M=4.21; Self-studies helps the student to perform well in tests; N=220, M=4.05; Self-studies encourages the curiosity in students; N=220, M=4.41. Furthermore, results directed that Self-studies build a sense of responsibility in the students has the highest mean score in mean analysis of Role of self-studies learning at university level.

Table 2: Mean analysis of Impact of self-studies learning on the students of university level

Statements	N	Mean
I rely on own self in completing my study tasks	220	4.70
I find information from wide variety of sources	220	4.55
I study according to my plan of action	220	4.42
I focus on most interested areas	220	4.16
I generate questions to test understanding about topic	220	4.72
I write summary that I listen during lecture	220	3.96
I think of a title while reading any material	220	4.13
I solve my difficulties by myself confidently	220	4.60
I improve my grades through individual-study	220	4.27
I manage my time for study	220	4.91
I can talk about current issues in the class	220	4.17
I check my work for errors before submitting it	220	4.25
I read lesson fluently in the class	220	1.78
I complete my assignment well individually	220	2.43
I am quick learner in doing home task	220	3.42

Table 2 shows the mean score of Impact of self-studies learning on the students of university level. The table further represented that the mean score of I rely on own self in completing my study tasks; N=220, M=4.70, I find information from wide variety of sources; N=220, M= 4.55; I study according to my plan of action; N=220, M= 4.42; I focus on most interested areas; N=220, M=4.16; I generate questions to test understanding about topic; N=220, M= 4.72; I write summary that I listen during lecture; N=220, M=3.96; I think of a title while reading any material; N=220, M=4.13; I solve my difficulties by myself confidently; N=220, M=4.60 I improve my grades through individual-study; N=220, M=4.27; I manage my time for study; N=220, M=4.91; I can talk about current issues in the class; N=220, M=4.17, I check my work for errors before submitting

it; N=220, M=4.25; I read lesson fluently in the class; N=220, M=1.78; I complete my assignment well individually; N=220, M=2.43; I am quick learner in doing home task; N=220, M=3.42. Furthermore, results directed that I manage my time for study has the highest mean score in mean analysis of Impact of self-studies learning on the students of university level.

DISCUSSION

Self-studies have been identified as an effective method of promoting learning among university students. Self-study involves the use of independent study techniques such as researching, reviewing course materials, and practicing exercises on one's own. It provides an opportunity for students to take control of their own learning process and work at their own pace. Furthermore, self-study is essential for students to build their own intellectual curiosity and passion for learning.

Several studies have investigated the role of self-studies in promoting learning among university students. A study conducted by [Akhtar, Ali, and Baig \(2021\)](#) found that self-study had a significant positive effect on academic achievement among university students. The study involved a sample of 500 undergraduate students and used regression analysis to analyze the data. The study concluded that self-study skills were critical for academic success and suggested that universities should focus on developing self-study skills among their students. Similarly, another study by [Khalid, Waheed, and Farooq \(2021\)](#) investigated the role of self-studies in promoting learning among medical students. The study found that self-study was significantly associated with academic performance and positively impacted the learning outcomes of medical students. The study recommended that medical students should be encouraged to develop their self-study skills to enhance their academic performance. Moreover, self-study has also been found to have a positive impact on student engagement and motivation. A study by [Zulfiqar, Baig, and Memon \(2021\)](#) found that self-study skills were positively correlated with student engagement and motivation. The study suggested that universities should focus on developing self-study skills among their students to promote their motivation and engagement in the learning process.

In conclusion, self-study is an effective method of promoting learning among university students. It provides an opportunity for students to take control of their own learning process, develop their intellectual curiosity, and enhance their academic performance. Therefore, universities should focus on developing self-study skills among their students to promote their academic success and engagement in the learning process

CONCLUSIONS

It is concluded that self-studies help the students to broaden their thinking level so they able to complete assignments. It also helps them to learn freely at their desired time. Students perform well in all tests. Self-studies limit the interest of students and build a sense of responsibility in the students. Self-studies boost the students' self-esteem so they think that it is more fun than regular teaching. Students also make their own study material. Self-studies give opportunity to interact with the subject matter and develop good work ethic so students tend to retain more naturally in work. It is also concluded that students write summary that they listen during lecture and think of a title while reading any material. They solve difficulties by themselves confidently. Students also manage time for study and hence they improve grades through individual-study. Furthermore, after self-studies students can talk about current issues, read lesson fluently, complete assignment well individually and check work for errors before submitting in the class.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It is recommended that teachers may encourage students to use their thinking abilities in the class. Students may constantly practice and incorporated critical thinking into daily lessons. Students might make a study space for themselves by saving a work area or table that is assigned climate for self-studying. It is also recommended that for the better understanding of how students perceive responsibility for their own learning, is an essential first step in creating an effective environment in the class that contributes to students' self-studies. Students might separate material by subject into a progression of short meetings, isolated by brief breaks. Moreover, for applying some self-testing techniques is a great way to test what students know and identify areas that could use some work.

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